

The Role of Leadership, Organizational Citizenship Behavioral and Work Environment in Improving Employee Job Satisfaction

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ABSTRACT: Early 2020 was marked by the outbreak of the Covid 19 pandemic throughout the world in general and Indonesia in particular. All parties work together to be able to cope with the Covid 19 pandemic outbreak. One of the institutions that has an important role in handling the Covid 19 pandemic is an institution engaged in the health sector, such as independent practice places for health workers, community health centers, clinics, hospitals, pharmacies, blood transfusion units, health laboratories, optics, service facilities. Medicine for legal purposes, and traditional health care facilities (PP No. 47/2016 Article 4). All health facilities are making every effort to be able to provide assistance to reduce the spread of the COVID-19 pandemic. The purpose of this study is to analyze and determine the impact of leadership, organizational citizenship behavioral and work environment on employee job satisfaction at Dr. Rawap Inap Clinic. M. Suherman, University of Muhammadiyah Jember. The study population was all employees of the Rawap Inap Clinic dr. M. SUherman Universitas Muhammadiyah Jember, amounting to 70 employees consisting of doctors, nurses and administrative staff as well as office boys. The number of samples in this study were 34 respondents who had filled out a questionnaire sent by google form. The data analysis method used is multiple linear regression analysis. The results showed that the work environment has an effect on employee job satisfaction. Leadership and organizational citizenship behavioral do not have a significant effect on employee satisfaction.

KEYWORDS: Leadership; Organizational Citizenship Behavioral; Work Environment; Satisfaction

I. INTRODUCTION

The number of cases of the Covid-19 pandemic in Indonesia is still growing. As of the end of October 2020, there were 3,565 new cases, bringing the total cases of the Covid 19 Pandemic in Indonesia finally to 404, 048.

([https://www.google.com/search?q=\(Https%3A%2F%2Fhealth.detik.com%2Fberita-detikhealth%2Fd-5233677%2Fupdate-corona-indonesia-29-oktober-tambah-3565-kasus-baru-tembus-404048\)%2C+2020.&oq=\(Https%3A%2F%2Fhealth.detik.com%2Fberita-detikhealth%2Fd-5233677%2Fupd, 2020\)](https://www.google.com/search?q=(Https%3A%2F%2Fhealth.detik.com%2Fberita-detikhealth%2Fd-5233677%2Fupdate-corona-indonesia-29-oktober-tambah-3565-kasus-baru-tembus-404048)%2C+2020.&oq=(Https%3A%2F%2Fhealth.detik.com%2Fberita-detikhealth%2Fd-5233677%2Fupd, 2020))). This number

will continue to grow if all parties involved do not pay attention to and implement the health protocols that have been announced by the government. Health facilities as the frontline in the community also need to prepare facilities that can support to overcome the problem of this Covid 19 Pandemic. The first reference for the community to deal with health problems is usually using the existing health facilities around the community location. The role of these health facilities is very important in supporting the handling of the Covid-19 pandemic. Currently, the number of health facilities in Indonesia that have collaborated with the Social Security Administering Agency (BPJS) for Health already has 27,154 Health Facilities (Faskes). It consists of 21,196 units of First Level Health Facilities (FKTP) and 5,958 units of Advanced Level Health Facilities (FKTL). This number will still increase because there are still many hospitals that have not cooperated with BPJS Kesehatan.

(<https://databoks.katadata.co.id/datapublish/2017/10/12/berapa-jumlah-fasilitas-kesehatan-pelayanan-bpjs-kesehatan#, 2017>).

The existence of health facilities in collaboration with BPJS (Social Security Administering Agency) plays a very important role in dealing with the Covid-19 pandemic that occurred in Indonesia. The leadership of each unit of this health facility must continue to strive to be able to improve services to people who need facilities to overcome all health problems in general and the

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problems of the Covid 19 Pandemic in particular. Health facility employees such as doctors, nurses, administrative staff and other departments are required to continuously improve their performance in serving people who need health services.

Employee job satisfaction is an important thing that needs attention from organizational leaders or business entities in health facilities that work with BPJS. Why job satisfaction needs attention, this is because job satisfaction is directly related to employees who are doing their job. It has been explained that employees who are satisfied with their work then any work given will be completed on time. According to (Mangkunegara, 2010) job satisfaction is an employee's feeling towards work whether the employee feels happy or unhappy. (Azhad et al., 2015) stated that job satisfaction is a person's attitude towards the work he faces. There are several factors that can increase the job satisfaction of employees, among others: leadership, organizational citizenship behavior and work environment.

Leadership plays an important role in increasing employee job satisfaction in every organization they lead. Leaders whose speech and behavior are the same, then the behavior of leaders like this will be emulated and used as role models by their subordinates. A leader who always acts fairly towards all his employees will give his employees a feeling of pleasure. A good example of this leader will give employees a feeling of satisfaction at work. Research that discusses the relationship between leadership and job satisfaction, among others, was carried out by: (Effendy et al., 2017), (Nursaid, Qomariah, Sanosra, et al., 2020), (Atmojo, 2012), (Kosasih, 2018), (Purnomo & Cholil, 2010), (Riyanto et al., 2018), (Ratnasari & Dewi, 2014), (Baihaqi, 2015), (Wirda & Azra, 2012), (Bushra et al., 2011), (Ayu et al., 2017), (Arifah & Romadhon, 2015), (Effendy et al., 2017), (Habba et al., 2017), (Aydin et al., 2013), (Cerit, 2009), (Nirmalasari, 2014), (Purnomo & Cholil, 2010), (Brahmasari & Suprayetno, 2008), (Baihaqi, 2015), (Arifah & Romadhon, 2015), (Wirda & Azra, 2012), (Brury, 2016), (Lok & Crawford, 2004), (Riyanto et al., 2018), (Lumbanraja, 2009), (Kosasih, 2018), (Anggitaningsih & Handriyono, 2019), (Ayu et al., 2017), (Atmojo, 2012), (Bushra et al., 2011), (Ratnasari & Dewi, 2014), (Mujkić et al., 2014). Thus the hypothesis that can be developed is: H1: leadership has an effect on employee job satisfaction.

Organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) has a wider scope compared to individual employee commitments because the meaning of citizen itself is citizenship so that they have responsibility and love for work voluntarily and without supervision (Robbins, 2011). OCB behavior is not contained in employee job descriptions, but is highly expected, because it supports increasing the effectiveness and survival of the organization, especially in a business environment where competition is increasingly fierce. Employees who have OCB will have high loyalty to the organization where they work, and automatically will feel comfortable and safe in their work (Luthans, 2014). OCB is behavior-oriented and it is hoped that this behavior reflects the values that are internalized. The nature of OCB is pragmatic so that it can be applied to organizational management, especially those related to human resources. Several studies on the relationship between OCB and satisfaction include: (Angelina & Subudi, 2014; Arianto, 2017; Lestari & Ghaby, 2018; Lukito, 2020; Maryati & Fernando, 2018; Triyanto, 2009; Wijayati et al., 2019). Thus the hypotheses that can be developed are: H2: Organizational citizenship behavior has an effect on employee job satisfaction.

(Sedarmayanti, 2011) states that the work environment is an environment where employees do their daily work to carry out the duties of their superiors. A comfortable work environment will provide a sense of security and allow employees to work optimally. The work environment can certainly affect the emotions of employees. According to (Nitisemito, 2014) defines that the work environment is the overall tools and materials encountered, the surrounding environment in which a person works, work methods, and work arrangements both as individuals and as groups. The work environment is everything that is around work and can affect an employee in carrying out the tasks assigned to him (Farida, 2014). Thus it can be concluded that the work environment is a collection of work environments in a place that has an impact on employee morale, and productivity both positively and negatively. A comfortable environment will provide flexibility for employees to work better. Employees who work comfortably indicate that there is satisfaction in them. Thus a comfortable work environment can increase employee satisfaction.

Research (Riansari et al., 2012) with the title "The Influence of Compensation and Work Environment on Job Satisfaction and Employee Performance (Case Study of PT Bank Tabungan Pensiunan Nasional, Tbk. Malang Branch", found the results that there was a direct influence of the work environment on job satisfaction. Research (Sudibya & Utama, 2012) states that working environment conditions can increase job satisfaction for employees in the Bali Provincial Public Works Office. Several studies that also discuss the relationship between environment and satisfaction include: (Ardianti et al., 2018), (Lumentut & Dotulong, 2015; Maslichah & Hidayat, 2017; Pih & Tawas, 2016; Riansari et al., 2012; Sitinjak, 2018; Sudibya & Utama, 2012), (Nursaid, Qomariah, Sanosra, et al., 2020), (Fachreza et al., 2014), (Hidayat, 2018), (Pribadi, 2018), (Anggitaningsih & Handriyono, 2019), (Ratnasari & Dewi, 2014), (Wibowo et al., 2014), (Qomariah et al., 2020). Research hypotheses that can be developed are: H3: work environment affects job satisfaction

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Inpatient Clinic dr. M Suherman is one of the primary health facilities in Jember Regency which also participates in dealing with public health problems. During the Covid 19 pandemic, the Inpatient Clinic dr. M Suherman also took part in dealing with the Covid-19 pandemic problem faced by the community. In order to support the government's program in terms of health development during the Covid-19 pandemic, it is necessary for everyone to increase awareness, willingness, and ability to live a healthy life in order to realize an optimal degree of public health, especially in the academic community of the University of Muhammadiyah Jember. So the Inpatient Clinic dr.M.Suherman answers all the challenges and dynamics of the health of students, lecturers and employees in particular and society in general. To achieve health goals, health services and services are carried out by the government and the private sector. Inpatient Clinic Dr. M Suherman synergizes with the government as the spearhead in providing health services to the community during the Covid 19 pandemic. Data on health facilities in Jember Regency that participated during the Covid-19 pandemic presented in table 1.

Table 1. Development of Public Health Facilities in Jember Regency 2020

Medical Facility	Total
Hospital	13
Public Health Center	50
Integrated Healthcare Center	2876
Polindes	76
Primary Health Facilities	24

Source: Jember District Health Office 2020

Table 1 shows that the number of health facilities to deal with health problems is already large. The increasing number of health facilities makes the competition in terms of getting patients even tighter, so that the health service providers provided by health facilities must continue to be improved, especially when the COVID-19 pandemic is ongoing. Starting from the background and existing business phenomena, the parties Inpatient clinic dr. M. Suherman is required to continuously improve the performance of his employees in terms of serving health to the community. Good service from clinic staff will give satisfaction to patients. Satisfied patients will appreciate the clinic where they are treated. Patient satisfaction is the satisfaction of employees starting from doctors, nurses and all employees involved in handling patients. From the background and previous research that has been done by previous researchers, the formulation of the problem in this study are: (1) does leadership affect employee job satisfaction?; (2) does organizational citizenship behavior affect employee job satisfaction?; (3) whether the work environment has an effect on employee job satisfaction. While this study has a purpose is to determine and analyze the influence of leadership, organizational citizenship behavior, work environment on job satisfaction of Inpatient Clinic employees dr. M. Suherman, Muhammadiyah University of Jember.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Leadership Style

Leadership plays a very important role in organizational management. Leadership is needed by humans because of certain limitations in humans. This is where the need to lead and be led comes from. Leadership is defined in terms of individual characteristics, habits, ways of influencing others, position in the organization and perceptions of legitimate influence. Leadership is the ability to influence others to achieve goals with enthusiasm (Davis & Newstorm, 2008). Leadership is the process of influencing or setting an example to followers through the communication process in an effort to achieve organizational goals (Mu'ah, 2002).

Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)

Behavior carried out by an employee that exceeds formal work obligations, but has a good impact because it supports organizational effectiveness (Davis, 2007). (Robbins & Coulter, 2010) states that aspects of organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) consist of several aspects, including:

- Altruism is the behavior of helping co-workers who have difficulty in the situation at hand regarding company tasks and personal problems. This aspect provides assistance that is not the responsibility of the main task.
- Conscientiousness, is a behavior that shows more effort made by employees than the company's expectations. This behavior is voluntary without considering the rewards or rewards that will be received.

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c. Sportsmanship, is a tolerant behavior shown by employees when the company's conditions are less than ideal without raising objections. This behavior supports a positive climate at work because of the behavior that is more polite and cooperative with others.

d. Courtesy is the behavior of maintaining good relations with co-workers to avoid personal problems, and tends to show caring behavior for others.

e. Civic Virtue is a behavior that dedicates itself to corporate responsibilities such as following changes in the organization, taking the initiative to recommend a change for the sake of efficiency and company progress.

Work Environment

The work environment is a place where employees perform activities every day. The work environment is said to be good or appropriate if humans can carry out activities optimally, healthy, safe and comfortable. (Hasibuan, 2016) states that the work environment is everything that is around the workers that can affect them in carrying out the tasks assigned. (Sedarmayanti, 2011) states that the work environment is the tools and materials encountered, the surrounding environment in which a person works, his work methods, and work arrangements both as individuals and as groups. The physical work environment is the physical condition in the company around the workplace, such as air circulation, wall color, security, space for movement and others. The physical work environment is all the circumstances around the workplace, which affect employees either directly or indirectly. So it can be concluded that the physical work environment is all kinds of physical or tangible conditions that exist around the workplace, including air circulation, wall color, security, space for movement that affect workers either directly or indirectly on the tasks assigned to them (Rivai, 2009).

Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is a pleasant or unpleasant emotional state in which employees view their work (Handoko, 2010). Job satisfaction reflects a person's attitude towards his job. This can be seen in the positive attitude of employees towards work and everything that is faced in the work environment. The personnel department or management must constantly monitor job satisfaction, because this can affect absenteeism, labor turnover, morale, complaints and other vital personnel problems. Job satisfaction is a positive emotional state from evaluating one's work experience (Simamora, 2006). Job dissatisfaction arises when these expectations are not met. Job satisfaction has many dimensions, in general are satisfaction in the work itself, salary, recognition, relationship between supervisors and workers, and opportunities for advancement. Each dimension produces an overall feeling of satisfaction with the work itself (Azhad et al., 2015). The absolute level of satisfaction does not exist, because each individual employee has a different standard of satisfaction (Mu'ah, 2002). This job satisfaction indicator can be measured by discipline, work morale, and low labor turnover, so employee job satisfaction is relatively good but on the contrary if discipline, work morale and labor turnover are large, then employee job satisfaction at the company is considered less.

III. RESEARCH METHODS

The research conducted on this scientific work is causality research. Causality research is research that has the main aim of proving a causal relationship or a relationship that affects and is influenced by the variables studied (Arikunto, 2011) (Arikunto, 2006). This study tries to explain the cause and effect of a subject matter and there is a hypothesis testing and analysis of the data obtained. The explanation carried out in this scientific work is to explain the influence of leadership style, OCB, work environment on job satisfaction.

Population as a generalization area consisting of objects/subjects that have certain quantities and characteristics (Ghozali, 2016). Population is all objects or individuals that have certain, clear and complete characteristics to be studied. The population of this study were all employees at the dr. Suherman Muhammadiyah University of Jember which consists of 70 doctors, nurses, administrative staff and cleaning staff. The sampling method used is the random sampling method. The random sampling method is a sampling technique in which all individuals in the population either individually or jointly are given the same opportunity to be selected as sample members. (Sugiyono, 2017). From a total population of 70 employees of the Inpatient Clinic, dr. M. Suherman, University of Muhammadiyah Jember, was sent a questionnaire using a google form. From the google forms that have been sent, as many as 34 employees have filled out the . thus the response to the answers of the respondents is $34/70 \times 100\% = 49\%$.

Validity is a measure that shows the levels of validity or validity of an instrument. A valid or valid instrument has high validity. On the other hand, an instrument that is less valid means it has low validity (Sekaran, 2006). Reliability refers to an understanding that an instrument is reliable enough to be used as a data collection tool because the instrument is already good. Reliability refers to the level of reliability of something. Reliable means trustworthy, so reliable. To determine or measure the

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intensity of the relationship between the dependent variable (Y) and several independent variables (X), the type of analysis used is multiple regression analysis.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Descriptive Statistical Results of Respondent Data

The results of the descriptive statistical analysis of respondents consisting of the gender of the respondents, the age of the respondents, the education level of the respondents from the employees of the Inpatient Clinic dr. M. Suherman University of Muhammadiyah Jember is presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Results of Descriptive Statistical Analysis

Indicator	Information	Total	Percentage
Gender	Man	4	12
	Woman	30	88
Age	20-30	16	47
	31-40	11	32
	41-50	7	21
	51-60	0	0
	SMA/SMK	1	3
Education	D3	18	53
	S1	14	41
	S2	1	3

Validity Test and Reliability Test

The validity test is used to test the extent to which the accuracy of the measuring instrument can reveal the concept of the phenomenon/event being measured. Questionnaire items are declared valid if the value of $r_{count} > r_{table} (n-2)$. Reliability test is used to test the extent to which the reliability of a measuring instrument can be used again for the same research. Reliability testing in this study is to use the alpha formula. For the validity test, it can be seen from the Corrected Item-Total Correlation which shows that the correlation between each indicator to the total construct score of each variable shows valid results, because $r_{count} > r_{table}$. So it can be concluded that all statement items are declared valid.

Reliability refers to an understanding that an instrument is reliable enough to be used as a data collection tool because the instrument is already good. Reliability refers to the level of reliability of something. Reliable means trustworthy, so reliable. The data reliability test can be seen in the results of Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted. The results of the reliability test showed that the values of Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted were all above 0.60. The results of the validity and reliability tests are presented in table 3.

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

To determine or measure the intensity of the relationship between the dependent variable (Y) and several independent variables (X), the type of analysis used is multiple regression analysis. The regression equation model used can be formulated as follows: $Y = -.911 + 0.315 X_1 + 0.311 X_2 + 0.422 X_3 + e$. The results of multiple linear regression analysis are presented in Table 4.

Table 3. Results of Validity Test and Reliability Test

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Item-Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
X11	56.1176	32.895	.627	.900
X12	56.2059	33.381	.440	.904
X13	56.4412	30.678	.682	.896
X21	56.4118	31.159	.635	.898
X22	56.4118	31.401	.656	.897

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X23	55.9706	33.181	.484	.903
X31	56.8824	30.713	.523	.905
X32	56.2353	29.761	.794	.891
X33	56.2647	30.867	.713	.895
Y11	56.3529	30.841	.679	.896
Y12	56.7059	29.426	.691	.896
Y13	56.3235	31.256	.593	.900
Y21	56.2941	34.093	.386	.906
Y22	56.2059	33.259	.542	.902
Y23	56.1176	32.955	.522	.902

Table 4. Results of Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

No	Variable	Regression Coefficient	Standart Error
1	Constant	-.911	2.347
2	Leadership (X1)	.315	.210
3	OCB (X2)	.311	.228
4	Work environment (X3)	.422	.230

Hypothesis Test

The hypothesis in this study was tested for truth by using a partial test. The test is carried out by looking at the t-count statistics with the t-table statistical value and the significance level (p-value), if the significance level resulting from the calculation is below 0.10 then the hypothesis is accepted, otherwise if the significance level of the calculated results is greater than 0.10 then hypothesis is rejected. From the results of hypothesis testing, it is known that the environment. The results show that the work environment has an effect on employee job satisfaction. Leadership and OCB have no significant effect on employee satisfaction. The calculation of the research hypothesis test results is presented in table 5.

Table 5. t Test Calculation Results

No	Variable	Count Significance	Significance Level	t count	t table	Information
1	Leadership (X1)	.145	0.10	1.496	1.697	Not significant
2	OCB (X2)	.183	0.10	1.364	1.697	Not significant
3	Work environment (X3)	.076	0.10	1.836	1.697	Significant

DISCUSSION

The Effect of Leadership on Employee Satisfaction

The results of the hypothesis test indicate that the leadership variable has a statistical significance value of 0.145 and is greater than 0.10 and t count (1,496) < t table (1,697) which means that the hypothesis which states that leadership has an effect on job satisfaction is rejected. This also shows that leadership does not affect employee job satisfaction at the dr. Suherman Muhammadiyah University of Jember. Staff at the Clinic dr. M. Suherman University of Muhammadiyah Jember is satisfied with the work that is his duty so that the role of the leader here has no effect on employee job satisfaction. Job satisfaction reflects a person's attitude towards his job. This can be seen in the positive attitude of employees towards work and everything that is faced in the work environment (Rivai, 2009). Leadership plays a very important role in organizational management. Leadership is needed by humans because of certain limitations in humans (Mu'ah, 2002). This research is not in line with research conducted by : (Boamah et al., 2018), (Chang & Lee, 2007), (Pancasila et al., 2020), (Loke, 2001), (Madlock, 2008), (Shibru, 2011), (Voon et al., 2011), (Kim & Brymer, 2011), (Yun et al., 2007), (Paracha et al., 2012) which states that there is a relationship between leadership and job satisfaction. While the research that is in line is the research conducted by (Lok & Crawford, 2004) which states that leadership has no impact on job satisfaction.

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The Effect of Organizational Citizenship Behavior on Employee Satisfaction

The results of the calculation of the hypothesis test for the OCB variable show that the calculated significance value is 0.183 and is greater than 0.10 and t count (1.364) < t table (1.697). This means that the hypothesis which states that OCB has an effect on job satisfaction is rejected. This also shows that OCB does not affect employee job satisfaction at the dr. Suherman Muhammadiyah University of Jember. This OCB is the behavior of employees who do work sincerely and in accordance with SOPs and even exceeds the SOPs that have been set by the institution. Employees who have a high OCB, the work done will be done sincerely. This is because employees already have a high OCB so that it does not affect employee job satisfaction. Behavior carried out by an employee that exceeds formal work obligations, but has a good impact because it supports organizational effectiveness (Davis & Newstorm, 2008). While job satisfaction is the feeling of employees towards the work at hand (Azhad et al., 2015). Research that is not in line with this research is research conducted by: (Lestari & Ghaby, 2018), (Triyanto, 2009), (Arianto, 2017), (Susanti Gunawan et al., 2013). While research that is in line with this research is research conducted by (Lukito, 2020), (Maryati & Fernando, 2018) which states that OCB has no effect on employee job satisfaction.

The Effect of Work Environment on Employee Satisfaction

The results of the calculation of the hypothesis test for the work environment variable show that the calculated significance value is 0.076 and is smaller than 0.10 and t arithmetic (1.836) > t table (1.697). This means that the hypothesis which states that the work environment affects job satisfaction is accepted. This also shows that the work environment affects employee job satisfaction at the dr. Suherman Muhammadiyah University of Jember. A comfortable work environment will make employees able to carry out their duties well. Tasks that can be done properly and on time will give employees satisfaction. Research that is in line with this research is research conducted by: (Maslichah & Hidayat, 2017), (Sudibya & Utama, 2012), (Lumentut & Dotulong, 2015), (Sitinjak, 2018), (Pioh & Tawas, 2016), (Nursaid, Qomariah, Abadi, et al., 2020), (Wibowo et al., 2014). While research that does not support this research is research conducted by (Riansari et al., 2012), (Qomariah et al., 2020).

V. CONCLUSIONS, SUGGESTIONS AND LIMITATIONS

Based on the results of the analysis that has been done, the conclusions in this study are: (1) leadership has no effect on job satisfaction at the dr. M. Suherman, Muhammadiyah University of Jember. Therefore the Clinic dr. M. Suherman must continue to improve the role of leadership in increasing job satisfaction of employees in the clinic; (2) organizational citizenship behavior has no effect on job satisfaction of the dr. M. Suherman, Muhammadiyah University of Jember. Therefore, the OCB of the employees must be continuously improved and instilled in the employees; (3) the work environment affects the job satisfaction of the dr. M. Suherman, Muhammadiyah University of Jember. This shows that the working environment at the dr. M. Suherman is able to provide a sense of comfort so that employees feel satisfied at work.

Based on the results of the study, the suggestions that can be given are: (1) the work environment contained in the dr. M. Suherman University of Muhammadiyah Jember is able to provide satisfaction to employees. Thus the leadership of the Clinic dr. Suherman Muhammadiyah University of Jember is expected to continue to improve the environmental conditions in the clinic so that employees are more satisfied; (2) for leadership variables and organizational citizenship behavioral variables that do not affect job satisfaction need serious attention from the leadership; (3) For future research, it is necessary to add variables that are not discussed in this study, such as employee commitment and work motivation

The limitation of this research is the response rate of the dr. Suherman Muhammadiyah University of Jember is still low at only 49% who respond to questionnaires sent via google form, this needs attention for further research to add respondents.

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